

Appendix for the Paper: Graph Representation Learning for Multi-Task Settings: a Meta-Learning Approach

A Episode Design Algorithm

Algorithm 1 contains the procedure for the creation of the episodes for our meta-learning procedures. The algorithm takes as input a batch of graphs (with graph labels, node labels, and node features) and the loss function balancing weights, and outputs a *multi-task episode*. We assume that each graph has a set of attributes that can be accessed with a *dot-notation* (like in most object-oriented programming languages).

Notice how the episodes are created so that **only one task is performed on each graph** (which implies that we only need labels for one task for each graph). This is important as in the inner loop of our meta-learning procedure, the learner adapts and tests the adapted parameters on one task at a time. The outer loop then updates the parameters, optimizing for a representation that leads to fast *single-task adaptation*. This procedure bypasses the problem of learning parameters that *directly* solve multiple tasks, which can be very challenging.

Another important aspect to notice is that the support and target sets are designed as if they were the training and validation splits for training a single-task model with the classical procedure. This way the meta-objective becomes to train a model that can generalize well.

B Additional Experimental Details

In this section we provide additional information on the implementation of the models used in our experimental section. We implement our models using PyTorch [8], PyTorch Geometric [4] and Torchmeta [3]. For all models the number and structure of the layers is as described in Section 4.2 of the paper, where we use 256-dimensional node embeddings at every layer.

At every cross-validation fold the datasets are split into 70% for training, 10% for validation, and 20% for testing. For each model we perform 100 iterations of hyperparameter optimization over the same search space (for shared parameters) using Ax [1].

We tried some sophisticated methods to balance the contribution of loss functions during multi-task training like GradNorm [2] and Uncertainty Weights [5], but

we saw that usually they do not positively impact performance. As an example, a GNN model trained for GC and LP with the classical procedure and using GradNorm, achieves results on GC, NC, and LP, that are on average 0.5% higher than the same model trained without GradNorm. However, a GNN model trained for NC and LP with the classical procedure and using GradNorm achieves results that are 0.8% lower than the same model trained without GradNorm. A similar behaviour happens by applying Uncertainty Weights, and, when the improvements were positive, they would never be higher than 1.7%. [10] also observe that when the multiple losses are of the same form, e.g. all cross-entropies, then these techniques tend to not bring any performance improvements. Furthermore, in the few cases where they increase performance, they work for both classically trained models, and for models trained with our proposed procedures. We then set the balancing weights to $\lambda^{(GC)} = \lambda^{(NC)} = \lambda^{(LP)} = 1$ to provide better comparisons between the training strategies.

The experiments were run on a Nvidia 1080Ti GPU, and on a CPU cluster equipped with 8 cpus 12-Core Intel Xeon Gold 5118 @2.30GHz, with 1.5Tb of RAM.

Linear Model. The linear model trained on the embeddings produced by our proposed method is a standard linear SVM. In particular we use the implementation available in Scikit-learn [9] with default hyperparameters. For graph classification, we take the mean of the node embeddings as input. For link prediction we take the concatenation of the embeddings of two nodes. For node classification we keep the embeddings unaltered.

Deep Learning Baselines. We train the single task models for 1000 epochs, and the multi-task models for 5000 epochs, with early stopping on the validation set (for multi-task models we use the sum of the task validation losses or accuracies as metrics for early-stopping). Optimization is done using Adam [6]. For node classification and link prediction we found that normalizing the node embeddings to unit norm in between GCN layers helps performance.

Algorithm 1 Episode Design Algorithm

Input: Batch of n randomly sampled graphs $\mathcal{B} = \{\mathcal{G}_1, \dots, \mathcal{G}_n\}$

Loss weights $\lambda^{(GC)}, \lambda^{(NC)}, \lambda^{(LP)} \in [0, 1]$

Output: Episode $\mathcal{E}_i = (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)})$

$\mathcal{B}^{(GC)}, \mathcal{B}^{(NC)}, \mathcal{B}^{(LP)} \leftarrow$ equally divide the graphs in \mathcal{B} in three sets

{Graph Classification}

$\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(GC)}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(GC)} \leftarrow$ randomly divide $\mathcal{B}^{(GC)}$ with a 60/40 split

{Node Classification}

for \mathcal{G}_i **in** $\mathcal{B}^{(NC)}$ **do**

 num_labelled_nodes $\leftarrow \mathcal{G}_i$.num_nodes $\times 0.3$

$\mathcal{N} \leftarrow$ divide nodes per class, then iteratively randomly sample one node per class without replacement and add it to \mathcal{N} until $|\mathcal{N}| = \text{num_labelled_nodes}$

$\mathcal{G}'_i \leftarrow \text{copy}(\mathcal{G}_i)$

\mathcal{G}_i .labelled_nodes $\leftarrow \mathcal{N}$; \mathcal{G}'_i .labelled_nodes $\leftarrow \mathcal{G}_i$.nodes $\setminus \mathcal{N}$

$\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(NC)}$.add(\mathcal{G}_i); $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(NC)}$.add(\mathcal{G}'_i)

end for

{Link Prediction}

for \mathcal{G}_i **in** $\mathcal{B}^{(LP)}$ **do**

$E_i^{(N)} \leftarrow$ randomly pick negative samples (edges that are not in the graph; possibly in the same number as the number of edges in the graph)

$E_i^{1,(N)}, E_i^{2,(N)} \leftarrow$ divide $E_i^{(N)}$ with an 80/20 split

$E_i^{(P)} \leftarrow$ randomly remove 20% of the edges in \mathcal{G}_i

$\mathcal{G}'_i^{(1)} \leftarrow \mathcal{G}_i$ removed of $E_i^{(P)}$

$\mathcal{G}'_i^{(2)} \leftarrow \text{copy}(\mathcal{G}'_i^{(1)})$

$\mathcal{G}'_i^{(1)}$.positive_edges $\leftarrow \mathcal{G}'_i^{(1)}$.edges; $\mathcal{G}'_i^{(2)}$.positive_edges $\leftarrow E_i^{(P)}$

$\mathcal{G}'_i^{(1)}$.negative_edges $\leftarrow E_i^{1,(N)}$; $\mathcal{G}'_i^{(2)}$.negative_edges $\leftarrow E_i^{2,(N)}$

$\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(LP)}$.add($\mathcal{G}'_i^{(1)}$); $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(LP)}$.add($\mathcal{G}'_i^{(2)}$)

end for

$\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)} \leftarrow \{\mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(GC)}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(NC)}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(LP)}\}$

$\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)} \leftarrow \{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(GC)}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(NC)}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(LP)}\}$

$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{(GC)} \leftarrow \text{Cross-Entropy}(\cdot)$; $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{(NC)} \leftarrow \text{Cross-Entropy}(\cdot)$

$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{(LP)} \leftarrow \text{Binary Cross-Entropy}(\cdot)$

$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)} = \lambda^{(GC)} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{(GC)} + \lambda^{(NC)} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{(NC)} + \lambda^{(LP)} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{(LP)}$

Return $\mathcal{E} = (\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)}, \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)}, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{E}_i}^{(m)})$

Our Meta-Learning Procedure. We train the single task models for 5000 epochs, and the multi-task models for 15000 epochs, with early stopping on the validation set (for multi-task models we use the sum of the task validation losses or accuracies as metrics for early-stopping). Early stopping is very important in this case as it is the only way to check if the meta-learned model is overfitting the training data. The inner

loop adaptation consists of 1 step of gradient descent. Optimization in the outer loop is done using Adam [6]. We found that normalizing the node embeddings to unit norm in between GCN layers helps performance.

Table 1: Results of a neural network trained on the embeddings generated by a multi-task model, to perform a task that was not seen during training by the multi-task model. “ $x, y \rightarrow z$ ” indicates that the multi-task model was trained on tasks x and y , and the neural network is performing task z .

Task	Model	Dataset			
		ENZYMES	PROTEINS	DHFR	COX2
GC, NC \rightarrow LP	CI	56.9 \pm 3.9	54.4 \pm 1.4	61.2 \pm 2.2	59.8 \pm 0.4
	iSAME	77.3 \pm 4.5	88.5 \pm 1.8	99.8 \pm 1.8	97.1 \pm 2.0
	eSAME	78.9 \pm 2.8	89.1 \pm 1.5	99.7 \pm 2.2	95.8 \pm 3.3
GC, LP \rightarrow NC	CI	69.1 \pm 1.2	57.3 \pm 1.6	58.3 \pm 9.3	68.9 \pm 10.7
	iSAME	73.3 \pm 2.1	59.2 \pm 2.5	77.6 \pm 1.6	78.1 \pm 4.6
	eSAME	79.1 \pm 1.7	64.7 \pm 3.0	76.1 \pm 2.7	76.9 \pm 3.3
NC, LP \rightarrow GC	CI	47.1 \pm 2.4	75.3 \pm 1.5	77.5 \pm 3.1	79.9 \pm 3.4
	iSAME	48.5 \pm 5.5	76.1 \pm 2.3	76.1 \pm 3.7	79.7 \pm 5.1
	eSAME	56.6 \pm 3.1	74.6 \pm 2.7	77.1 \pm 3.6	79.3 \pm 6.2

Table 2: Results for a single-task model trained in a classical supervised manner (CI), and a **linear** classifier trained on the embeddings generated by a model trained with an ablated “single-task” version our meta-learning strategies ((a)iSAME, (a)eSAME).

Task	Model	Dataset			
		ENZYMES	PROTEINS	DHFR	COX2
NC	CI	87.5 \pm 1.9	72.3 \pm 4.4	97.3 \pm 0.2	96.4 \pm 0.3
	(a)iSAME	87.3 \pm 0.8	81.8 \pm 1.6	96.6 \pm 0.3	96.1 \pm 0.4
	(a)eSAME	87.8 \pm 0.7	82.4 \pm 1.6	96.8 \pm 0.2	96.5 \pm 0.6
GC	CI	51.6 \pm 4.2	73.3 \pm 3.6	71.5 \pm 2.3	76.7 \pm 4.7
	(a)iSAME	50.8 \pm 2.9	73.5 \pm 1.2	73.2 \pm 3.2	76.3 \pm 4.6
	(a)eSAME	52.1 \pm 5.0	72.6 \pm 1.6	71.6 \pm 2.4	75.6 \pm 4.1
LP	CI	75.5 \pm 3.0	85.6 \pm 0.8	98.8 \pm 0.7	98.3 \pm 0.8
	(a)iSAME	81.7 \pm 1.7	84.0 \pm 1.1	99.2 \pm 0.4	99.1 \pm 0.5
	(a)eSAME	80.1 \pm 3.4	84.1 \pm 0.9	99.2 \pm 0.3	99.2 \pm 0.7

C Full Results for the Generalization of Node Embeddings

Table 1 contains results for a neural network, trained on the embeddings generated by a multi-task model, to perform a task that was not seen during the training of the multi-task model. Accuracy (%) is used for node classification (NC) and graph classification (GC); ROC AUC (%) is used for link prediction (LP). The embeddings produced by a model trained with SAME lead to higher performance (up to **35%**), showing that our procedures lead to models that can generate more informative node embeddings with respect to the classical end-to-end training procedure.

D Ablation Study - Full Results

Table 2 shows the results for the ablated “single-task” versions of SAME (i.e., the full results related to Figure 4 of the main paper). For every task, we train a **linear classifier** on top of the embeddings produced by a model trained using our proposed methods, and compare against a network with the same architecture trained in a classical manner. For all three tasks,

a **linear** classifier on the embeddings produced by a model trained with our methods achieves comparable, if not superior, performance to an end-to-end model. In fact, the linear classifier is never outperformed by more than 2%, and it can outperform the classical end-to-end model by up to 12%. These results highlight the impact of designing support and target sets to encourage generalization.

Table 3 presents the results of a neural network trained on the embeddings generated by a model trained with an ablated version of iSAME and eSAME to perform a task that was unseen during training. The ablated version of iSAME and eSAME is obtained by using the support and target set design that encourage generalization, but by not applying the multiple separate single-task adaptations in the inner loop. In particular all tasks are performed concurrently on all graphs both in the inner loop and the outer loop (leading to a *multi-task* version of the traditional MAML and ANIL procedure, but with our design of support and target sets). Finally, Table 4 shows the results in terms of the multi-task performance (Δ_m) metric [7] of the latter ablated version of SAME. For both experiments, we notice that the results are not significantly different from those of the non-ablated iSAME and eSAME (Table 1 in Appendix, and Table 2 of the paper), indicating that iSAME and eSAME increase the sample efficiency of the training procedure as they can lead to a model generating embeddings that can reach the same results but by only applying one task per graph (and hence only requiring the labels for one task per graph).

References

- [1] E. Bakshy, L. Dworkin, et al. Ae: A domain-agnostic platform for adaptive experimentation. In *NeurIPS ML Sys Workshop*, 2018.
- [2] Z. Chen, V. Badrinarayanan, et al. Gradnorm: Gradient normalization for adaptive loss balancing in deep multitask networks. In *ICML*, 2018.
- [3] T. Deleu, T. Würfl, et al. Torchmeta: A Meta-Learning library for PyTorch. *arXiv*, 2019.
- [4] M. Fey and J. E. Lenssen. Fast graph representation learning with PyTorch Geometric. In *ICLR RLGW Workshop*, 2019.
- [5] A. Kendall, Y. Gal, et al. Multi-task learning using uncertainty to weigh losses for scene geometry and semantics. In *CVPR*, 2018.
- [6] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. In *ICLR*, 2015.
- [7] K.-K. Maninis, I. Radosavovic, et al. Attentive single-tasking of multiple tasks. In *CVPR*, 2019.
- [8] A. Paszke, S. Gross, et al. Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library. In *NeurIPS*. 2019.
- [9] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, et al. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 2011.
- [10] S. Vandenhende, S. Georgoulis, et al. Revisiting multi-task learning in the deep learning era. *arXiv*, 2020.

Table 3: Results of a neural network trained on the embeddings generated by a multi-task model, to perform a task that was not seen during training by the multi-task model. The multi-task model has been trained with an ablated version of iSAME and eSAME (which we refer to as (a)iSAME and (a)eSAME), where no single-task adaptation is performed, but a multi-task version of the traditional meta-learning procedure is applied. “ $x,y \rightarrow z$ ” indicates that the multi-task model was trained on tasks x and y , and the neural network is performing task z .

Task	Model	Dataset			
		ENZYMES	PROTEINS	DHFR	COX2
GC,NC \rightarrow LP	(a)iSAME	75.6 ± 3.3	88.3 ± 1.2	98.4 ± 0.9	95.1 ± 1.7
	(a)eSAME	79.4 ± 2.8	89.2 ± 1.6	97.4 ± 0.7	95.3 ± 1.4
GC,LP \rightarrow NC	(a)iSAME	71.8 ± 2.5	59.7 ± 3.2	76.4 ± 2.3	79.1 ± 2.3
	(a)eSAME	79.5 ± 1.6	63.8 ± 2.1	77.0 ± 2.1	78.9 ± 2.1
NC,LP \rightarrow GC	(a)iSAME	42.3 ± 5.5	75.8 ± 2.6	76.9 ± 4.4	78.3 ± 7.5
	(a)eSAME	53.6 ± 3.5	75.6 ± 2.1	77.3 ± 2.8	77.7 ± 5.2

Table 4: Δ_m (%) results for a **linear** classifier trained on the node embeddings generated by a model trained with an ablated version of iSAME and eSAME (which we refer to as (a)iSAME and (a)eSAME), where no single-task adaptation is performed, but a multi-task version of the traditional meta-learning procedure is applied.

Task			Model	Dataset			
GC	NC	LP		ENZYMES	PROTEINS	DHFR	COX2
✓	✓		(a)iSAME	-3.2 ± 0.4	2.8 ± 1.3	-0.4 ± 0.3	-0.5 ± 0.2
			(a)eSAME	0.5 ± 1.1	1.7 ± 0.5	-0.5 ± 1.2	-1.5 ± 0.5
✓		✓	(a)iSAME	1.5 ± 2.9	-0.9 ± 1.1	0.1 ± 4.1	-0.2 ± 3.1
			(a)eSAME	3.0 ± 1.7	-2.5 ± 1.6	-0.4 ± 3.5	-0.4 ± 4.2
	✓	✓	(a)iSAME	4.3 ± 2.8	4.5 ± 1.1	-0.2 ± 6.2	-0.6 ± 4.2
			(a)eSAME	3.1 ± 0.4	5.0 ± 1.1	-0.1 ± 5.9	-0.5 ± 4.1
✓	✓	✓	(a)iSAME	1.0 ± 1.2	2.7 ± 0.3	-1.2 ± 2.4	-1.1 ± 2.9
			(a)eSAME	0.4 ± 1.2	1.1 ± 0.3	-1.3 ± 1.1	-0.9 ± 1.1